

Mini Review : Hazard Factors in Tourism on The South Coast of Java for The Safety and Security of Visitors

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Abstract

On the South Coast of Java, Indonesia, natural conditions such as tropical cyclones, wind speed and maximum wave height are significant factors that influence beach safety. Apart from physical factors, there are also biological dangers such as sea snakes, sea urchins, coral reefs and jellyfish which can threaten tourists. This article aims to explain the parameters that pose a threat to beach tourism on the southern coast of Java, with a focus on physical and biological factors. Based on the analysis, factors such as rip currents, tidal waves and toxic marine biota are the dangers that most often result in accidents on beaches. Apart from that, the importance of risk assessment in coastal areas was also discussed to increase the safety of beach tourism. This assessment includes beach characteristics, number of visitors, emergency rescue factors, and safety management readiness, all of which play a role in preventing accidents and ensuring the sustainability of beach tourism destinations.

Keywords : Beach tourism, Physical hazards, Biological hazards

Introduction

Tourism activities place a significant emphasis on tourists' protection and safety. According to Mahagangga et al. (2013), in order for tourists to experience a sense of satisfaction while traveling, it is very necessary for them to provide themselves with a sense of security and comfort. As stated by Pizam and Mansfeld (1996) in Hermawan (2017), the primary consideration that tourists take into account while selecting a tourist site is the level of safety that is available there. There are a number of islands in Indonesia that are affected negatively by the creation of tropical cyclones, and Java Island is one of those islands. Natural catastrophes such as floods, landslides, and other damage that create economic losses in terms of infrastructure, housing, social culture, and across sectors are caused by tropical cyclones. These natural disasters also cause deaths and disappearances. Many of the beaches along the southern coast of Java are popular tourist destinations, and the majority of the people who live there are fishermen. It is therefore imperative that the coastal waters of South Java be prioritized with regard to security and safety concerns. According to Mahsunah (2019), the variables that have the most impact on the

environment are the wind speed conditions and the maximum wave height. In addition to the physical factors, biological elements, particularly the harmful biota that are found along the coast, can also be a source of danger in tourism activities. The activities that are associated with tourism along the shore have the potential to bring about interactions between humans and the biota that live there. These interactions can take place under specific circumstances, such as when the biota are defending their territory or searching for prey. In light of the information presented above, the purpose of this article is to provide an explanation of the factors that represent a threat to beach tourism, particularly along the South Coast of Java. This discussion is restricted to simply the physical and biological aspects of the situation.

Potential Physical Hazards

Rip current

Physical factors are tangible elements that are generally easier to evaluate since they can be observed with the naked eye and have standards that are reasonably comparable to those of other factors being evaluated. tourist destinations along the seaside may be subject to a variety of potential physical dangers. Rip currents, tidal waves, waves, and tides are the elements that make up the physical elements that can be found in Sayang Heulang Beach. The awareness that visitors have regarding the possibility for physical risks is still limited. In Sayang Heulang, only 25% of tourists listed rip currents, 30% mentioned waves, 20% named hatchling waves, and 25% mentioned ebb and flow as potential physical risks. However, rip currents and hatchling waves are the potential physical hazards that frequently result in the loss of life of individuals.

A strong rush of water that flows towards the sea from around the coast, typically through the surf line, is known as a rip current. Rip currents can occur on any beach that has broken waves. According to Suleiman and Soehardi, as cited in Kalay et al. (2018), the normal flow speed of a rip current is between 2.5 and 3.0 meters per second, which is fast enough to be faster than the pace at which a human swimmer can swim. In the same manner that water always follows the shape of its container, seawater also follows the shape of the base and morphology of the beach, as well as the direction in which waves are arriving while they are approaching. Following the formation of an angle between the beach and the waves that are flowing in from the ocean, a current will emerge that is parallel to the beach. There is a point at which this parallel current moves in a convergent manner, which results in a reasonable amount of backflow. According to the findings of a number of studies, rip current is the primary contributor to beach tourism accidents in a number of nations (Kumar and Prasad, 2014).

The Plunging and the Swell Wave

Wind waves and swell waves are the two types of gravity waves that are generally recognized in the scientific community. According to Habibi et al. (2018), wind waves are examples of gravity waves that are produced when energy is transferred from the wind to the surface of the water. Wavelength is a function that determines the separation or dispersion of waves. According to Bhowmick et al. (2011), waves with the longest wavelengths depart the wave creation area at a faster rate, and the undulation of the sea surface that is induced by wave dispersion is referred to as swell. After the wave has reached a water depth that is approximately 1.3 times the height of the wave, the wave will collapse or break, which is referred to as a breaking wave. There is a depth of around 1.3 meters at which a wave that is as high as one meter will break. Plunging waves, spilling

waves, surging waves, and collapsing waves are the four categories that are used to categorize the different forms of breaking waves (USACE, 1984). When the wave suddenly slows down and the wave quickly rises to a higher height, the plunging type of wave is generated. This type of wave is formed on beaches that are steeper. According to Webb (2019), the peak of the wave is higher than the rest of the wave, bends forward, and then breaks with a quick loss of energy.

Tidal wave

The vertical movement (regular and repeated up and down) of water mass particles from the surface to the lowest section of the bottom is one of the natural phenomena that take place in the sea (Duxbury et al., 2002). Tides are one of the natural phenomena that take place in the coastal environment. This movement is brought about by the gravitational pull, also known as the attractive force, that exists between the earth and the moon, the earth and the sun, or the earth with the moon and the sun. According to Pariwono (1985), the sea tides in Indonesia can be classified into two distinct characteristics: single tides, which are predominant in the seas of the western Indonesian region, and double tides, which are predominant in the waters of the eastern Indonesian region. According to Haryono and Narni (2004), the features of the sea tides on the island of Java are as follows: partly mixed sea tides tend to double daily in Prigi, Cilacap, Jakarta, and Surabaya, and partly mixed tides tend to single daily around Jepara.

Possible Dangers to Biological Systems

Sea snakes

The class of animals known as reptiles and the order known as squamata are the ones that include sea snakes. According to Herbert et al. (2012), these cold-blooded species, also known as poikilotherms, are classified with amphibians as members of the herpetofauna group, which is synonymous with the term "reptiles." This particular snake has a small mouth and head, and in general, sea snakes carry a very potent poison. The fangs of this snake are the delivery mechanism for the poison that it possesses. Sea snakes are one of the potential biological dangers that visitors who are participating in activities that include sea waters may face. This is due to the fact that the toxin that this snake produces is extremely hazardous.

The sea urchins

Sea urchins are a type of marine crustacean that are frequently discovered on beaches with white sand and are considered to be a possible biological threat. In most cases, sea urchins will conceal themselves in coral. This is done in order to conceal the result of exposure to intense light (Fuji et al. 1985, as cited in Kasim 1999). Those tourists who do not wear footwear are at risk of being poked by sea urchin spines. This is because the spines of sea urchins are sharp and can easily penetrate the skin. This results in a fever, which poses a risk to the toxin that is found in the spines. A therapy with ammonia or a weak acid, such as citrus and vinegar, can be used to neutralize the toxin. According to Romimohtarto and Juwana (2001), the risk is at the tip of the spines, which enter the soles of bare feet and disintegrate in the blood, causing pain and swelling in the affected area for the individual.

Coral reef

A symbiotic relationship exists between the animal group belonging to the phylum Cnidaria and the ecosystems that in the form of enormous deposits are known as coral reefs. Coral is a group of polyp organisms that are responsible for the production of lime, which is calcium carbonate. Almost all hermatypic corals are colonies, with numerous individual coral animals or polyps occupying small containers called kolarites inside a huge structure (Prasetya, 2003). Corals can be colonial or they can be found on their own. The coral reefs that are generated from limestone deposits have abstract shapes, which means that there are some coral shapes that are sharp and extremely deadly. When tourists are participating in sports like as swimming, snorkeling, or diving, they run the risk of being injured by these sharp coral forms. Even coral formations that are not sharp can provide a risk of injury to tourists if they are fashioned in such a way that they can produce bruising or other external sores.

The jellyfish

Scyphozoa jellyfish are coelenterates that live in the ocean. They can be found in the form of polyps that are connected to the bottom of the water or in the form of medusae that drift freely through the water. They are transparent, have a body that is squishy like gelatin, and contain a significant amount of water. Because they have the ability to induce itching on the skin when they are touched, these jellyfish are considered to be nuisance creatures in coastal waters, particularly in regions that are used for recreational purposes. The presence of stinging cells or nematocysts in the epidermal tissue, which can be seen on the tentacles as well as in other areas of the body, is the root cause of this condition.

Beach Tourism Safety

This is a time when the safety aspect of beach tourism is becoming increasingly crucial due to the huge number of incidents that occur when people are traveling on the beach. It is now a requirement of the society that a tourist attraction must ensure the safety of its visitors in order for the place to continue to be attractive and profitable. According to Suharto (2016), the management is responsible for providing protection against dangers and accidents in the tourism industry, beginning with the stage of visitor arrival and continuing through activities that take place at the tourist destination until the return of those who have visited. According to Chiang (2000), safety assurance is the most important factor for tourists to consider when selecting a tourist destination. Chiang (2000) also states that safety assurance is the most important factor in determining the growth and development of a tourist destination. Additionally, the value of excellence is a factor that will determine the quality of a tourist destination.

To guarantee the security of beach tourism, it is necessary to conduct an evaluation in order to identify the variables that pose a risk in the coastal region. Characteristics of the beach, the number of visitors, factors related to emergency rescue, factors related to risk prevention, and factors related to safety preparation are all included in the evaluation. The prevention of drowning and swimming injuries can be aided by a risk assessment program that is effectively implemented. The program has the potential to increase the minimal number of lifeguards and contribute to the improvement of beach management, both of which will be to the benefit of beach managers, lifeguards, and other parties affected by the situation (ILSE 2005).

Conclusion

Safety and security are very important aspects in beach tourism activities, especially in the southern coastal region of Java which is vulnerable to physical and biological hazards. Some significant physical hazards include rip currents, high waves, and tides, while biological hazards include dangerous marine life such as sea snakes, sea urchins, coral reefs, and jellyfish. To ensure tourist safety, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive risk assessment of factors that could endanger safety in coastal tourism areas, as well as implementing an effective safety program. Guaranteed safety will be a determining factor in visitors' choice of tourist destination and contribute to the sustainability of that destination.

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